

DATA STANDARDS: THE LINK BETWEEN DESIGN AND TEST

James P. Hanna
Design and Diagnostics Branch
Microelectronics Reliability Division
Rome Laboratory
Griffiss AFB, NY 13441-5700

Abstract

Few standard representations of engineering, design, and test information exist to foster exchange and re-use in any reasonable fashion during the process of developing and fielding electronic systems. Significant costs are associated with regenerating and translating original data to/from the various Computer Aided Design and Test (CAD/CAT) tools that are used during system development. Industry standard data representations that provide for the exchange of engineering information between design and test activities must be developed. The exchange of this information is critical to the application of test automation technology and concurrent engineering to next and future generation electronic systems.

Introduction

As microelectronic components and printed circuit boards become more and more complex the costs associated with supporting these products continues to increase. It is estimated that testing and support costs comprise more than 70% of the life-cycle cost of today's complex microelectronics. With complexity increasing, it is becoming more critical to reduce the cost of testing and supporting electronic systems.

System design practices that bring test engi-

neers and design engineers together during the design process to assure that adequate attention is paid to Design For Testability (DFT), are becoming more accepted. This Integrated Product Design (IPD) approach will prove effective not only in assuring due consideration to testability issues, but will also assure improved diagnostics and reduce back-end testing and support costs.

One of the keys to improving this IPD process lies with capturing and re-using the original design data throughout the product life-cycle. Industry standard representations of the design information, testing requirements, diagnostic information, test patterns, and timing information are essential to provide for the maximum data portability and re-use. This data, along with design to test automation tools will provide the necessary automation links between design and test activities.

This paper discusses the design to test data representations that are being developed by Rome Laboratory in concert with representatives of the Computer Aided Design/Test (CAD/CAT) Industry and various DoD and Government Agencies under the auspices of the IEEE.

Background & History

In 1984 Rome Laboratory sponsored a feasibility study for developing a tester independent

database to support the capture and maintenance of design data for automated document generation and automated test program generation for complex microelectronics. In 1985-1989 the Very High Speed Integrated Circuit (VHSIC) program office sponsored the design and development of the Tester Independent Support Software System (TISSS) through Rome Laboratory. TISSS provides a software system, built around a tester independent database, which integrates automation tools for the storage and retrieval of design and test data, automated generation of MIL-M-38510 documents, and automated test program generation for complex microcircuits.

The TISSS database utilized Industry standard data representations where they existed. The Initial Graphic Exchange Specification (IGES) is used for document drawings. The Electronic Data Interchange Format (EDIF) is used for schematic information. The VHSIC Hardware Description Language (VHDL) is used for behavioral and structural models. Where no Industry standard existed TISSS defined new representations. The TISSS Test Vector Language (TVL) and the TISSS Test Description Language (TDL) were developed under the TISSS program to fill the voids for tester and CAD independent representations of this information. TISSS uses the IGES, EDIF, and TDL data for automated document generation and the TDL and TVL data for automated test program generation.

In 1989 the TISSS data formats began IEEE standardization under Project Authorization Request (PAR) 1029. The TISSS TVL served as the starting point for what was to become the Waveform And Vector Exchange Specification (WAVES). This PAR was jointly sponsored by the Automatic Test Program Generation (ATPG) subcommittee of the Standards Coordinating Committee 20 (SCC20) and the Design Automation Standards Subcommittee (DASS) of the IEEE. The WAVES Analysis and Standardization Group (WASG) was formed to address this

initial PAR to develop a standard representation for the bidirectional exchange of digital stimulus/response data between design and test communities.

During the requirements gathering and definition phase it became obvious that the scope of interchanges needed between design and test was much broader than simply test stimulus and response. Additional requirements identified included the representation of diagnostic data that could be used for fault detection and localization, and information needed to support the unambiguous representation of hierarchical testing requirements for electronic systems.

Since the original PAR could not satisfy all of these requirements, a new set of PARs were submitted to the IEEE and 1029 became a family of standards that would cover the development of interchanges between design and test communities. The new PARs were: WAVES - PAR 1029.1 which continued with the original focus on digital stimulus and response, FDL - PAR 1029.2 Fault Detection and Localization, and TRSL - PAR 1029.3 a "glue" standard for representing test requirements for all electronic systems. The name of the working group was changed to the Test Analysis and Standardization Group (TASG) to more closely reflect the new scope of the committee.

In December of 1991 the broad balloting community of the IEEE approved WAVES as the Industry standard digital stimulus/response exchange format. The TASG is continuing information modeling and development of the FDL and TRSL formats. Each of the 1029 formats will be discussed in more detail later.

Problem Domain

Figure 1 illustrates the information typically exchanged between design and test activities. These activities include both physical and elec-

tronic design, simulation, and test.

There are currently many proprietary language formats used by various CAE/CAD tool vendors for representing and utilizing this data for design automation. One problem is that the data generated by one vendor's tool cannot be readily used by the tools of another vendor. Often translations between two vendor formats are incomplete due not only to format incompatibilities but, more importantly, due to incompatibilities in data content. Further, for electronic system life-cycle support, this proprietary data becomes obsolete as quickly as the rapid and unpredictable changes in the CAD industry occur.

Another problem is that no integrated solution exists to address the complete spectrum of engineering, design, and test activities. Users

may wish to exploit the strengths of various tool environments to provide a partial solution to these problems. To do so they must piece together disjoint tools and provide their own data translators and annotation methodologies. Since little attention has been paid to test automation, beyond low speed functional testing, these solutions do not adequately address the design-to-test data or the full requirements of test automation.

Until design and test information can be freely exchanged in electronic form between multiple tool environments it is unlikely that these problems will be solved. Industry standard information exchange formats will provide the mechanism for this free exchange of design and test data. Common exchange formats will also guard against data obsolescence. Since industry standards are developed by representatives of many interest groups, they tend to be more robust

Figure 1 Design and Test Information Flow

and more complete than proprietary formats which are typically designed to fill specific market niches.

Another quality that industry standards possess is inertia. Industry standards tend to evolve slowly rather than change by leaps and bounds. This is due to the large investment that users have in the tool base that utilizes the standard. Large changes in industry standards that have a broad tool base incur large expense for tool vendors. Since tool vendors comprise a fair portion of the committees that maintain these standards it is in their best interest to assure their stability.

The following sections will present and discuss three industry standard data representations that are in various stages of development and their potential impact on the above mentioned problem domain.

The Waveform And Vector Exchange Specification (WAVES)

WAVES, (IEEE Standard, 1029.1 - 1991), is a language for capturing and exchanging stimulus and expected response information (test vectors/signal histories) for digital microelectronics. WAVES provides a powerful and expressive language for representing test stimulus and response information in a standard, non-proprietary, format that can be readily transported among multiple simulation and test platforms. WAVES is capable of representing waveforms and vectors for all levels of digital electronic systems, and as such provides powerful support for concurrent engineering techniques.

WAVES provides a logic model of the waveform that represents events on signals as (state, strength, direction, relevance) 4-tuples in time. This model need not be fully populated; events on the waveform can be represented with only the information known at a given phase of product development. For example, during behavioral

modeling the waveform events may only have meaning with regard to their state in time; the rest of the model may be "filled out" as development proceeds. The flexibility in this representation is powerful, as it allows the waveform to mature as product development matures and provides a mechanism for capturing design decisions as they occur. WAVES also provides for the transport of stimulus and expected response data from design to test. The WAVES data portability issue is not only important for allowing the verification of the product "as built" (using the same waveforms used in the product development) it is also critical to the assurance of the integrity of test vector sets for tester re-hosting.

The Fault Detection and Localization (FDL)

FDL (IEEE PAR 1029.2) will provide a standard representation for diagnostic information needed in design and test automation environments for digital modules and Printed Circuit Boards (PCB). The purpose of the FDL PAR is to establish a standard way to represent fault dictionaries independent of proprietary CAD and tester environments. As such, FDL will provide for the interchange of this information among various design and test environments. Information represented using FDL includes that required to provide the capability for fault identification (fault type, fault location) and fault coverage. All of this data centers on information to support methods for fault detection and localization. FDL will equally apply to all levels of electronic systems and support general testing (digital, analog, mixed-signal).

FDL is being designed to work in concert with the other 1029 standards (WAVES, TRSL) as well as other industry standards. WAVES vector representations will be used for fault signature descriptions by the fault dictionary mechanisms of FDL. Where required, and applicable, FDL will provide "hooks" which will enable other information standards to be used in

conjunction with the FDL data formats to provide fuller coverage of the data needed for specific fault diagnosis methods (eg. Guided Probe, Signature Analysis, etc.).

The FDL working group (TASG) is currently developing and refining a language requirements document that is expected to be available in the third quarter of 1992. An information model of the data components and their interrelationships is being developed in EXPRESS. This model will serve as a tool for furthering the developments of the FDL language requirements as well as exploring rudimentary language implementation issues. The Information Model will also provide schema information for database representation support for FDL for electronic design and test data configuration management. Once the language requirements have solidified, work will begin on the development of an FDL Language Reference Manual (LRM) and prototype language implementations as an exchange mechanism.

The Test Requirements Specification Language (TRSL)

TRSL, (IEEE PAR 1029.3) is a proposed language standard for representing both product specific performance information and multi-level hierarchical testing requirements in a tester independent electronic format for digital, analog, and mixed-signal components and board modules. TRSL will provide a framework by which engineers can capture test requirement specifications at multiple levels of abstraction. This information will be used to document the test intent, test methods, and test sequencing in a form that is independent of test platform. This independent data format facilitates the re-use and transport of testing requirements among a variety of test environments.

TRSL provides a specification for test requirements (What tests must be performed), test

intent (Why a test is performed), test methods (How a test is performed), and all the electrical and timing performance characteristics. The unambiguous representation of this information is critical to the ability to apply automation tools in support of test program generation for electronic microcircuits, board modules, and systems.

The TASG has developed a TRSL language requirements document that is available for review. Also, an information model of the data components and their interrelationships is being developed in EXPRESS. This model will serve as a tool for furthering the developments of the language requirements as well as exploring rudimentary language implementation issues. The Information Model will also provide schema information for database representation support for TRSL for electronic design and test data configuration management. Once the language requirements and information model stabilize, work will begin on the development of a Language Reference Manual (LRM) and prototype language implementations as an exchange mechanism.

Conclusions

Standard interchange formats are necessary to provide a common basis for communicating design and test data between multiple tool environments. Integrated design and test tool based solutions that support concurrent engineering are not likely to be realized without non-proprietary, tool independent information interchange formats. Developing these standards through industry will assure that these interchange formats are robust and complete.

Attention must be paid to supporting and automating testing processes by providing data from design activities to test activities. Data standards will provide a crucial link that supports this flow of design information. Further, design and test engineers need to work together "up-

front" to assure that testability issues become design issues.

References

[1] L. J. Falkenstorm, et al, "Tester Independent Support Software System (TISSS)", Proc. IEEE International Test Conference, 1985

[2] James P. Hanna, "A New Methodology for Test Program Set Generation and Re-hosting", Proceedings of the IEEE Automatic Testing Conference, 1991.

[3] Robert G. Hillman, "WAVES: A Simulation and Tester View", Proc. IEEE Automatic Testing Conference, 1990.

[4] Antonette S. Pettinato and William E. Russell Jr, "Computer-Aided Design and Tester Independence of Test Information Standards", Proc. IEEE Automatic Testing Conference, 1990.

[5] ATPG/ATE Interface Requirements, IEEE PAR 1029, Prepared by the Test Analysis and

Standardization Group of the Design Automation Standards Subcommittee and the Standards Coordinating Committee Number 20 of the IEEE, July 30, 1991.

[6] Draft WAVES Standard, IEEE PAR 1029.1, Prepared by the Test Analysis and Standardization Group of the Design Automation Standards Subcommittee and the Standards Coordinating Committee Number 20 of the IEEE, December 12, 1990.

[7] FDL Requirements, IEEE PAR 1029.2, Prepared by the Test Analysis and Standardization Group of the Design Automation Standards Subcommittee and the Standards Coordinating Committee Number 20 of the IEEE, March 10, 1992.

[8] TRSL Requirements, IEEE PAR 1029.3, Prepared by the Test Analysis and Standardization Group of the Design Automation Standards Subcommittee and the Standards Coordinating Committee Number 20 of the IEEE, February 19, 1992.